

Acoustic interactions in metamaterials formed by Phononic Crystals with locally resonant structure

María Pilar Peiró-Torres¹, Sergio Castiñeira-Ibáñez^{2,4}, Javier Redondo³, Juan Vicente Sánchez-Pérez^{4,a)}

¹ BECSA. Ciudad del Transporte II. C/ Grecia, 31, Castellón (Spain)

² Universitat de València. Departamento de Ingeniería Electrónica; Avda. Universidad s/n Bujassot, Valencia (Spain).

³ Universitat Politècnica de València. Instituto de Investigación para la Gestión Integrada de zonas Costeras, Paranímf 1, Grao de Gandia, Valencia (Spain)

⁴ Universitat Politècnica de València. Centro de Tecnologías Físicas, Acústica, Materiales y Astrofísica, División acústica. Camino de Vera s/n, Valencia (Spain)

The emergence of materials artificially designed to control the transmission of waves, generally called metamaterials, has been a hot topic in the field of acoustics for several years. The design of these metamaterials is usually carried out by overlapping different wave control mechanisms. An example of this trend is the so-called Locally Resonant Sonic Materials, being one of them the Phononic Crystals with local resonant structure. These metamaterials are formed by sets of isolated resonators in such a way that the control of the waves is carried out by resonances and by the existence of Bragg bandgaps, which appear due to the ordered distribution of the resonators. Their use is based on the creation of resonance peaks to form additional non-transmission bands mainly in the low frequency regime, usually below the first Bragg frequency. However, the manipulation of these metamaterials must be done with care because some interference effects may appear between the resonances and the Bragg bands when they are working in nearby frequency ranges. In this work, using a Phononic Crystal formed by Helmholtz resonators, we report on the existence of these interferences and their physical principles, at the same time that we present possible solutions to avoid them. To this end, we have developed numerical models based on the finite elements method, and the results have been successfully verified by means of accurate experimental results obtained under controlled conditions.

Acoustic metamaterials are generally defined as artificial structures with physical effective properties, related to the control of elastic waves, not found in nature. In the past decade, a great effort has been made in order to analyze their novel and rich physics and the large number of potential applications¹⁻¹⁶. An important kind of acoustic metamaterials is that formed by Phononic Crystals (PC) with locally resonant structure, formed by periodic arrays of Helmholtz Resonators (HR)¹⁷⁻²². These metamaterials are included inside the known as Locally Resonant Sonic Materials^{11, 23-25}. In these crystalline metamaterials, the existence of bandgaps (BG) in the low frequency regime is restricted due to the requirement of dimensional similarity between the wavelengths and lattice constant of the PC. But this limitation is overcome with the creation of sub-wavelength Locally Resonant bandgaps (LRG), through the inclusion of HR in the array. Although BG and LRG are usually far from each other in the domain of frequencies, in some cases the overlapping of both is interesting to obtain a broadband transmission loss, as in the case of noise control. In these cases, some interactions can appear between both BG and LRG, which have been reported by some authors^{26, 27} but their physical principles have not yet been analyzed in depth.

In this work we present a research about the underlying Physics in BG/LRG interactions, developed theoretically by means of a simplified two-dimensional (2D) numerical model based on the Finite Elements Method (FEM), and supported by accurate experiments carried out in controlled conditions. Although the study is focused to the case of 2D PC formed by rigid scatterers in air, usually called Sonic Crystals^{28, 29}, the results obtained can be extended to any device in which both BG and LRG are interacting.

To analyze these interactions we have developed the geometry shown at the top of the Figure 1(a). The considered 2D domain of length $L=1\text{m}$ is formed by 3 scatterers with external radius, r_{ext} , and separated by the lattice constant of the array formed, a . The scatterers can work as closed cylinders or cylindrical HR with a cross-sectional area of the neck, A_n , and length of the neck, L_n . HR can be placed in the numerical domain with the necks oriented in any direction, but for the sake of brevity we will analyze here only two cases: 0° and 180° with respect to the direction of propagation of an incident plane wave travelling from left to right, calling hereinafter $\text{HR}0^\circ$ and $\text{HR}180^\circ$ respectively. In all cases, the scatterers are confined between two linear boundaries separated by the lattice constant of the array, a . The measurement point is located at $d=0.2\text{m}$ from the center of the last scatterer, far enough to avoid near-field effects behind the sample. The vertical boundaries are surrounded by Perfectly Matched Layers (PML)³⁰ to simulate the Sommerfeld radiation conditions. In the horizontal boundaries of the model we have imposed periodic boundary conditions. Considering these conditions the incident wave is not reflected by the horizontal boundaries, but the scattered waves reproduce the effect of a semi-infinite 2D

Sonic Crystal formed by 3 rows of scatterers arranged in a square array. Finally, since we have considered all types of scatterers to be acoustically rigid, the Neuman boundary condition (zero sound velocity) is applied to their surfaces.

To visualize first the LRG/BG acoustic interactions, we have considered an array with a BG centered at 2000Hz with three different kinds of scatterers: (i) closed cylinders; (ii) HR0° with a LRG centered at 1000Hz; and (iii) HR0° with a LRG at 385Hz. The values of the general parameters of the array are, $a=0.08\text{m}$ and $r_{\text{ext}}=0.0315\text{m}$, and the particular values for each HR0° are, $L_n=0.0058\text{m}$ (0.04m) and $A_n=0.02\text{m}$ (0.004m) for the second and the third case respectively. A detail of the scatterers is presented at the bottom of Figure 1(a). In all cases, the attenuation spectrum, usually called Insertion Loss (IL), has been calculated. The obtained results are presented in Figure 1(b). It can be observed that when the LRG is far from the BG in the frequency domain (array (i) vs. array (iii)) the size of the BG is almost equal, being the BG/LRG interaction almost negligible. However, when BG and LRG are close (array (i) vs. array (ii)), a reduction in the BG appears, which would be greater the closer LRG and BG are. In this latter case the range of affection of the interference extends to a larger frequency range than that occupied by the LRG itself.

FIG.1: (a) Numerical 2D model designed to analyze the BG/LRG interactions. The typology of the scatterers used is shown at the bottom; b) IL spectra for the three considered arrays

The interference produced in the transmitted field considering only a single scatterer has been analyzed first. Three would be the potential mechanisms involved: (i) the absorption; (ii) a change in directivity; or (iii) a phase shift. The first and third mechanisms have been analyzed using a numerical model that simulates an impedance tube with anechoic ends, as can be seen in the inset of Figure 2(a), while the scheme shown at the top of Figure 2(b), which consists of a typical anechoic configuration used to measure the directivity of the scattered field, has been numerically developed to analyze the change in the directivity. In the latter model, a plane wave traveling from left to right impinges on each of the

considered scatterers located in the center of the domain, allowing to estimate the scattered field in the circular measurement zone.

Concerning the absorption, at the top of the Figure 2(a) it can be seen that the IL spectra for a single $HR0^\circ$ or $HR180^\circ$ are exactly the same, showing the resonance peak centered on 1000Hz. But its range of affection in the frequency domain does not correspond to the interference phenomenon to be analyzed, which affects a larger frequency range outside the absorption itself, as can be seen in Figure 1(b) for the $HR0^\circ$ 1000Hz case. This result allows us to rule out absorption as the main mechanism responsible for interference. In the case of the change in the directivity, the results are shown at the bottom of Figure 2(b), where the sound pressure scattered by both $HR0^\circ$ and $HR180^\circ$ is represented. It can be seen that both sound fields are completely different being their IL spectra exactly the same, as stated above. That means that the directivity does not affect the attenuation produced by HR, and this result allows us to discard the directivity mechanism as well. Finally, the results of the Cylinder/ $HR0^\circ$ and Cylinder/ $HR180^\circ$ phase shifts are shown at the bottom of Figure 2(b). One can observe that both spectra are equal, being this mechanism compatible with the range of affection shown in Figure 1(b). Then we can conclude that the phase shift could be the main responsible for this interference.

FIG.2: Analysis of the influence of the three possible mechanisms responsible for interference analyzed for single scatterers; (a) absorption spectra (upper part) and phase shift spectra (lower part) for $HR0^\circ$ and $HR180^\circ$. In the inset you can see a schematic of the numerical model used; (b) an outline of the anechoic model used to simulate the directivity of both HR (upper part); the directivity results can be seen at the bottom.

Next we will focus our analysis on the physics involved in the phase shift mechanism for a single scatterer, considering first the phenomenon of resonance in isolation, without scattering. For this we use the numerical model presented at the top of Figure 3(a), which considers a single HR not located in the transmitted wave path. The numerical domain consists of a rectangle with rigid boundaries,

and an HR with dimensions: $a=0.04\text{m}$; $b=0.03\text{m}$; $c=0.01\text{m}$; $d=0.01\text{m}$, which supposes a resonance peak at 1000Hz , is considered. An incident plane wave travelling from left to right is reflected at the rigid right boundary, and the sound pressure level is measured in a point located at $e=0.85\text{m}$ from this boundary. The results can be seen at the bottom of Figure 3(a). In absence of the HR the eigenmodes would appear for frequencies given by

$$f = nc/(2L) \quad (1)$$

where n is an integer, c the speed of sound and L is the length of the domain. However, in the presence of HR the eigenmodes are displaced within a frequency range around the resonance frequency of the HR. Thus, within the range of affection of the HR the modes are shifted forward or backward for frequencies below or above the resonance frequency, respectively.

FIG.3: Analysis of the influence of the phase shift on the BG/LRG interference; (a) Phase shift for the pure resonance case for a single HR. An outline of the model is presented at the top. The variation of SPL is represented at the bottom; (b) Phase shift for the case of resonance plus scattering for a single scatterer. The numerical model is presented at the upper part. At the center, the phase shift Cylinder/HR0° is shown. The lower part represents the distance displacement, Δx , associated with the phase shift; (c) BG/LRG interference, showing with arrows the displacement of frequencies in the BG. The normalization to 1 of the BG for both arrays formed either by cylinders or by HR0° can be seen in the inset; (d) ELC as a function of frequency, calculated from the phase shift (continuous black line) and frequency shift (red dotted line).

The next step is the analysis of the resonance along with the scattering by adapting the model of Figure 1(a) to the case of a single scatterer (top of Figure 3(b)), and determining the phase shift of the transmitted wave at the measurement point. The phase shift is represented at the middle of Figure 3(b), and one can check that the range of affection is similar to both the previous case and the one shown in Figure 1(b). This phase shift can be interpreted as a difference of distances, in which the transmitted wave in both HR0° and cylinder cases would have the same phase state. Thus, a distance shift, Δx , can be easily calculated as a function of the frequency, f , and the phase shift previously obtained, φ , as follows:

$$\Delta x = \frac{\varphi c}{2\pi f}$$

The absolute value of Δx has a maximum at the resonance frequency and decreases as we move away from it, maintaining in a range of affection at both higher and lower frequencies, as shown at the bottom of Figure 3(b).

The concept of distance shift becomes important when applied to the case of PC, where BG appears. In these devices, the location of the BG depends on the lattice constant of the array, a , which in turn determines the position of the scatterers. Due to the phase shift induced by the HR, the waves would arrive to the scatterers in a different state of phase, and Δx could be understood as if the lattice constants considering either HR0° or cylinders were different. In other words, BG/LRG interference is due to a phase shift that makes the distance between scatterers seen by the wave, a' , different from the real one, a . In the following we will call a' Equivalent Lattice Constant (ELC). This means that the BG is not destroyed, but shifted in frequency. If we consider the HR0°1000Hz array with $a=0.08\text{m}$, where the BG/LRG interference is more noticeable, this fact is represented at Figure 3(c) where the displacement of frequencies in the BG is marked with arrows.

Two different methods to estimate the trend of variation of the ELC as a function of frequency have been considered. The first is the phase shift method, already used in the case of a single scatterer, applied to the case of the considered PC. The second is the frequency shift method, in which both BG are normalized to 1 (see the inset of Figure 3(c)), and from the frequency shift between both BG the corresponding ELC is estimated. The results for some frequencies above the resonance peak are represented at Figure 3(d) on the basis of the starting value of a ($a=0.08\text{m}$). The same trend is observed with both methods, equal to the case of a single scatterer, where there is a variation in the ELC in the range of affection of the HR. In the example considered the BG of the HR0° array moves towards high frequencies because $a' < a$ since the BG is above the LRG. Due to a' depends on the frequency, an increasing of the real lattice constant would compensate the effect of the phase shift induced by HR0° and would produce a displacement of the BG again towards low frequencies. Similarly, if the BG were

located below the resonance peak, a' would be smaller than a , and the BG would shift to low frequencies. To correct this, the value of the PC lattice constant should be decreased.

To validate these numerical predictions we have carried out accurate experiments in an anechoic chamber using a directional white sound source (S), and measuring at a distance $d=1\text{m}$ behind the sample. In the inset of Figure 4 we show an outline of the experimental set up used. A comparison between the numerical and experimental IL results for three cases can be seen in Figure 4: At the top, a PC with closed cylinders with $a=0.08\text{m}$, where the first BG is centered at 2000Hz and starting around 1050Hz . At the middle, a PC made of $\text{HR}0^\circ$ 1000Hz , where the displacement of the first BG, which now starts around 1550Hz , is observed. At the bottom one can see a PC with $\text{HR}0^\circ$ but with a higher lattice constant ($a=0.09\text{m}$), where the first BG has moved towards low frequencies, starting at 1450Hz . In this latter case the size of the starting BG has not been completely recovered, only its position in the frequency range due to the increasing of the lattice constant that reduce the filling fraction of the PC. The experimental results are in quite good agreement with the numerical simulations, considering the use of an ideal numerical model. Note that, although the ELC is a function of frequency, a single variation of the lattice constant produce the displacement of the BG.

FIG.4: Numerical (continuous black line) vs. experimental (red dashed line) IL results for three PC cases: cylinders with $a=0.08\text{m}$, $\text{HR}0^\circ$ with $a=0.08\text{m}$ and $\text{HR}0^\circ$ with $a=0.09\text{m}$. An outline of the experimental set up is shown at the bottom left.

Summarizing, in this work we have analyzed in depth the BG/LRG interference phenomenon in PC formed by HR. We have performed numerical simulations validated with accurate experiments carried out under controlled conditions. The existence of HR as scatterers, when the LRG is close to BG, induces a phase shift in the transmitted wave that can be understood as a virtual change in the lattice constant of the array, which is greater or smaller than the real one depending on the frequency considered, and which we have called Equivalent Lattice Constant (ELC).

M.P.P.T. is grateful for the support of pre-doctoral Grant by the “Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad” of Spain through reference No. DI-15-08100.

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